

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF CYCLOALKANE IN NATURE METHODS OF MEETING AND OBTAINING

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Along with open-chain saturated hydrocarbons, there are also closed-chain hydrocarbons there is These are known as cycloalkanes. The general formula is C_nH_{2n} . Cycloalkanes are another also known as: cycloparaffins, alicyclic compounds, naphthenes, cyclones, polymethylenes. If the molecule consists of one ring - bicyclic, if it consists of three rings - if it is cyclic, if it consists of many rings, it is called polycyclic compounds. Monocyclic compounds consists of a methylene group, depending on the number of the methylene group, it was once trimethylene, tetromethylene, also called pentamethylene etc. Currently, according to the Geneva nomenclature is being named.

For example, C_3H_6 -cyclopropam, C_4H_8 -cyclobutane, C_5H_{10} -cyclopentane. Cycloalkanes are some is in the composition of oils. Therefore, they are also called naphthenes. Five and six members cycloalkanes were first isolated from oil and its properties by V.V. Markovnikov studied. Some cycloalkanes are also part of essential oils. For example, terpenes and camphors. They are also found in the leaves and petals of many plants. Composition of essential oils are not the same, mainly depending on the weather conditions of the place where they grow. South In France, Italy and Turkey, essential oil extraction has become a major industry. There are several ways to extract essential oils from plants. For example: compression method. This in Sicily, essential oils are manually pressed from lemon and orange peels. Another method is steam extraction, 500 kg of rose oil is extracted by this method in Bulgaria in a year. Obtainable. Cycloalkanes are active against dihalogenated derivatives of saturated hydrocarbons in the laboratory metals are affected. It's like a viral reaction. Gustavson was the first to do this determined. That is why it is also called the Gustavson method. Paraffin metal catalysts with his participation, it is also possible to get fucked straight. For example: in the presence of a platinum catalyst cyclopentane is obtained. Cycloalkanes can also be extracted from petroleum. Benzene cyclohexane is obtained by hydrogenation. Lithium amalgam instead of zinc to obtain cyclobutene can be used:

Physical and chemical properties of cycloalkanes. Their properties are similar to those of alkanes, the first two representatives are gas cyclopropane and cyclobutane, the rest are liquids and solids. As the mass of cycloalkanes increases, the boiling point, temperature and density also increase. Cycloparaffins differ from paraffins by having two hydrogen atoms less. Enter into the reaction differs from alkanes. Alkanes undergo substitution reactions. And cycloalkanes it enters into the substitution reaction and the joining reaction. A small ring to the coupling reaction compounds enter faster, and cycloalkanes with large rings enter the replacement reaction faster. They also interact with halogens. This reaction is a substitution

reaction. Cycloalkanes reacts with halogenic acids as well. N.D. Zelinsky dehydrogenation of cyclohexane to benzene takes Cycloalkanes also undergo a nitration reaction.

In conclusion, I will say that cycloalkanes have their place in organic chemistry. For example: if cyclohexanol is obtained by hydrogenation of phenol, cyclohexanone is oxidized, and oxidation is continued dibasic carbonic acid is formed. As a result of this reaction, several different organic substances is being taken. Dyes and medicines are obtained from cycloalkanes. Cyclopropane for anesthesia in medicine is used. Hexachlorocyclohexane is also used as an insecticide in agriculture.

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